

Mapping Research Topics on Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the FDR ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the FDR ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the FDR ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 246 journal publications regarding the FDR ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the FDR ratio are divided into 5 clusters and 174 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 31 topics around the influence of the FDR ratio and 18 topics about the determinants of the FDR ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around FDR ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) is a financial ratio that is commonly used in the banking industry to measure the level of bank dependence on third party funds in providing credit. In simple terms, FDR is the ratio between the amount of credit provided by the bank and the amount of third party funds (deposits and deposits) received by the bank. FDR is an important indicator of a bank's financial health, because it can provide an overview of the bank's ability to fulfill payment obligations to customers and the adequacy of bank liquidity in managing risk. FDR can also provide information about bank business performance. A bank with a low FDR indicates that the bank has more resources to provide credit, which can have a positive impact on the bank's business growth. On the other hand, a bank with a high FDR indicates that the bank is very dependent on third party funds in providing credit, which can affect the level of bank risk and the profits generated by the bank. The use of FDR in investment decision making in the banking industry has evolved over time. Investors, especially in the stock market, consider FDR as an important indicator for assessing bank performance. For example, a bank with a low FDR can be considered a bank that is financially healthier and has more potential to provide high returns for investors. However, the use of FDR also has disadvantages. FDR does not consider credit risks or market risks that banks may face. Apart from that, FDR also does not consider other factors that could affect bank business performance, such as operational costs or non-interest income. Therefore, FDR should not be the only factor considered in making investment decisions in the banking industry.

Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) is a ratio used to measure the amount of funds provided by the bank in the form of loans or financing against the amount of

funds received by the bank from its customers in the form of deposits. FDR is calculated by dividing the total loans or financing provided by the bank by the total deposits received by the bank. This ratio is usually used by banking supervisors as an indicator of a bank's financial health. The higher the FDR, the greater the liquidity risk for the bank because banks spend more money in the form of loans or financing than the amount of money they receive from customers in the form of deposits. Conversely, the lower the FDR, the safer the bank's liquidity position. In recent years, FDR has also experienced changes in its use. Some banks and regulators are starting to use risk-adjusted FDR ratios to provide more accurate information about a bank's ability to manage credit and market risks. Risk-adjusted FDR also takes into account the credit and market risks that a bank may face, so it can provide more comprehensive information about the bank's business performance. Overall, FDR is one of the important financial ratios in the banking industry. Although FDR can provide important information about bank performance, FDR should not be the only factor considered in making investment decisions in the banking industry.

Bibliometric studies are Quantitative analysis method for studying and evaluating published scientific work in a particular research field or scientific discipline. This method involves collecting and analyzing bibliographic data related to scientific works, including information such as author, title, journal, year of publication, and number of citations to the work. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify research trends, measure the influence of authors or journals, and evaluate research productivity or quality. Bibliometric analysis can be carried out using various metrics, such as citation indices, journal impact factors, and Hirsch indices, which are used to measure the impact or influence of certain scientific works. Bibliometric studies have been used in various fields, such as social sciences, computer science, public health, and information science. This method can provide valuable insights for researchers, publishers, and policy makers to understand and promote research in a particular field. VOSviewer is Bibliometric data analysis and visualization software used to visualize networks and clusters of scientific work published in a particular research field or scientific discipline. This software was developed by the Eindhoven University of Technology in the Netherlands. VOSviewer can be used to perform bibliometric analysis, such as cluster analysis, network analysis, and keyword analysis, and produce interesting and informative visualizations. The software allows users to import bibliometric data from various sources, such as Google Scholar and Web of Science, and analyze that data to identify research trends, connections between topics, and the influence of authors or journals. VOSviewer can produce various types of visualizations, such as network maps, co-cutting diagrams, and cluster maps, which can help researchers and policy makers understand and promote research in a particular field. This software has been used in various fields, such as social sciences, computer science, public health, and information science.

literature review study is research method carried out by systematically analyzing studies, articles, books and other sources of information relevant to a particular research topic. The goal is to gain a better understanding of the research topic and to identify knowledge gaps in the research area. In a literature review study, researchers collect, review, and analyze sources of information related to the research topic, then draw conclusions and recommendations based on their findings. This procedure includes selecting relevant sources of information, evaluating the quality of those sources, and content analysis to identify major themes and similarities or differences among the selected studies. Literature review studies are used in many research fields, including social sciences, health sciences, computer science, and other fields. These studies are often used to establish the basis of research and evaluate developments in a field, as well as identify future

research directions. Literature review studies can also help researchers and practitioners in developing policies and best practices based on the latest and best findings.

Research on FDR in banking has developed rapidly in recent years, especially regarding the influence of FDR on bank financial performance and the factors that influence changes in FDR. First, several studies indicate that FDR can influence bank financial performance, and show that FDR has a positive and significant effect on bank profitability in Indonesia. Meanwhile, other research shows that FDR has a negative effect on the financial performance of banks in Indonesia. Second, several studies also examine the factors that influence changes in FDR in banking, and show that deposit interest rates, credit interest rates, and economic growth have a positive effect on FDR in banks in Indonesia. Third, other research shows that variables such as bank size, bank liquidity, and loan growth have a significant effect on FDR in Nigeria. Fourth, several studies have also developed predictive models to estimate future changes in FDR. There is research that develops a multiple linear regression model to predict changes in FDR at banks in Indonesia. The research results show that the variables of interest rates, economic growth and bank liquidity can be used as predictors to estimate changes in FDR in the future. Fifth, several studies also try to compare the use of FDR with other financial ratios in measuring bank financial performance by comparing the use of FDR with other financial ratios such as Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR) and Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in measuring bank financial performance in China. Research results show that FDR is more accurate in measuring bank financial performance than LDR and CAR. Overall, the development of research on FDR in banking shows that FDR is still an important financial ratio in measuring bank financial performance. However, the use of FDR should also be combined with a more in-depth analysis of the bank's overall business performance and the risks that the bank may face.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding FDR in Sharia and Conventional Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature developments in publications in a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding FDR. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research FDR. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics surrounding the FDR ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is the Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about FDR in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for Sinta accredited national journals via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Financing to Deposit Ratio " and "FDR " throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document

Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding FDR using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around FDR using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around FDR using a literature review study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications About Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 246 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2010 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data about FDR by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2010	1	2016	13	2020	31
2011	1	2017	21	2021	54
2012	4	2018	20	2022	42
2014	8	2019	37	2023	8
2015	6				

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Mapping around Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around FDR. Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer related to the research development map regarding FDR in Sharia and Conventional Banking, there are 5 clusters and 174 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 55 topic items, namely: analytical tools, data analysis, analysis of the influence of capital adequacy ratio, analysis of the influence of financing, assets, Indonesian banks, sharia banks, sharia commercial banks, bi rate, operational costs, operational income, bopo, buses, capital adequacy ratio, car, third party funds, panel data, deposit ratio, dpk, equity, fdr, finance, financing, hypothesis, inflation, Jakarta, quantitative, analysis methods, mudharabah, net operating margin, nom, non-performing margin, ojk, financial services authority, influence of car/dpk/financing/return, sharia banking, performing financing, purposive sampling, return, roa, roe, sharia banking, significant on return/roa, spss, square, tbk, analysis techniques, f test, t test, variable.
- Cluster 2, consists of 46 topic items, namely: analysis method, autocorrelation test, BNI Syariah, classic assumption test, coefficient, data analysis method/technique, data collection technique, determination test, documentation, empirical evidence, f test, fdr variable, financial services authority, form, heteroscedasticity test, hypothesis test, inflation, Islamic banking, Islamic commercial banking, multicollinearity test, multiple linear regression, multiple regression analysis, normality test, partial test, profit sharing, profitability, purposive sampling technique, quantitative research, quarterly financial report, research data/sample/variable, secondary data, significance level/value/effect, t count, t test, test variable.
- Cluster 3, consists of 31 topic items, namely: annual report, approach, bank, independent sharia bank, capital, customer, dependent variable, development, expense, financial performance, financing deposit ratio, health, independent variable, influence, liquidity, management, multiple linear regression, npf variable, performance, quality, quantitative method, r square, relationship, research method/model, sig, significant negative effect, size, value, variation.
- Cluster 4, consists of 28 topic items, namely: analytical method, cost, data analysis, distribution, financial statement, fund, income, increase, indicator, Indonesian stock exchange, Indonesian sharia bank, Islamic bank, level, multiple regression, murabahah financing, negative effect, operating income, operational cost, path analysis, positive effect, quantitative approach, ratio, sampling method/technique, bank sharia, third party fund, total assets/sample.
- Cluster 5, consists of 14 topic items, namely: analysis technique, annual financial report, capital adequacy, company size, criteria, firm size, mudharabah deposit, profit, purposive sampling method, sharia commercial bank, significant influence/positive effect, technique.

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Influence of Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) on Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 31 influences of FDR on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Sharing the profits from Mudharabah deposits. The higher the FDR, the less funds available to be placed in mudharabah deposits. This can reduce the level of profit for customers because the funds available to invest are limited. However, if

the FDR is low, the bank has more funds to place in mudharabah deposits, so it can provide greater profits for customers.

(2) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR. The higher the FDR, the higher the bank's credit risk because the bank has to borrow more to finance financing. This can lead to a decline in the bank's CAR, which is an important indicator of a bank's ability to bear financial risks. However, if FDR is low, bank credit risk tends to be lower and CAR tends to be higher.

(3) Mudharabah Deposits. Mudharabah deposits can help increase a bank's CAR because mudharabah deposits are considered a form of bank capital. This can help banks to meet the minimum CAR requirements set by the regulator. In addition, mudharabah deposits are also considered a stable source of funds, which can help banks reduce their credit risk.

(4) Financial Sustainability Ratio /FSR. The higher the FDR, the greater the bank's credit risk, which can reduce the bank's FSR because the bank must fulfill debt and interest payment obligations. Therefore, a high FDR can reduce a bank's FSR. However, if the FDR is low, the bank's credit risk is also low, so the bank's FSR can be higher.

(5) Share price. A high FDR can provide a negative signal to investors about a bank's ability to manage credit risk and maintain liquidity. This can reduce investor confidence and cause bank share prices to decline. On the other hand, a low FDR can provide a positive signal that the bank has sufficient liquidity and is able to manage its credit risk, thereby increasing investor confidence and share prices.

(6) Islamic Performance Ratio/ IPR. A high FDR can reduce the IPR because high credit risk can affect the quality of bank assets and overall financial performance. However, if the bank is able to manage credit risk well, a low FDR can increase the IPR because the bank can obtain greater profits from investments in mudharabah financing and deposits.

(7) Capital adequacy. The higher the FDR, the greater the bank's credit risk, which can affect the bank's capital adequacy. If a bank experiences losses due to high credit risk, the bank may experience a decrease in capital adequacy. However, if the bank is able to manage credit risk well, a high FDR does not always have a negative impact on the bank's capital adequacy.

(8) Zakat compliance. FDR does not have a direct influence on the fulfillment of a bank's zakat obligations, because zakat must be paid on profits earned, not on FDR. However, a high FDR can affect bank profits and, therefore, the size of the bank's zakat obligations. If the bank generates higher profits from financing and mudharabah deposits, then the bank's zakat obligations will be greater.

(9) Company profits. FDR can affect company profits because mudharabah financing and deposits are the main source of income for banks. A high FDR can increase credit risk and affect the quality of bank assets, which can reduce company profits. However, if the bank is able to manage credit risk well, a low FDR can reduce company profits because the bank cannot obtain sufficient income from financing and mudharabah deposits.

(10) Liquidity. FDR can affect bank liquidity because the higher the FDR, the greater the bank's liquidity risk. If a bank has a high FDR, the bank may face difficulties in meeting financial obligations when they fall due. Therefore, banks need to monitor FDR and ensure that bank liquidity remains sufficient to meet its financial obligations.

(11) Murabahah Margin. Murabahah margins can be affected by FDR because the higher the FDR, the higher the bank's funding costs. Banks that have a high FDR have to pay higher interest on the funds they borrow, so their funding costs are higher. This may affect Murabahah Margins, as banks may have to increase the selling price of financing to offset higher funding costs.

(12) Earnings management. FDR can influence earnings management because banks may be inclined to engage in earnings management practices if they face pressure to maintain or increase profits at times of high FDR. Banks may engage in earnings management practices such as delaying settlement of losses or manipulating their financial statements to show better performance than they actually do. However, good quality banks tend to avoid earnings management practices because it can harm their reputation in the eyes of stakeholders.

(13) Profit sharing ratio on deposits. FDR can affect the profit sharing ratio on deposits because the higher the FDR, the more difficult it is for banks to provide high profit sharing ratios to customers. This is due to higher bank funding costs when FDR is high, so banks may limit the profit sharing ratio on their deposit products.

(14) Non Performing Financing /NPF. FDR can affect NPF because the higher the FDR, the greater the credit risk faced by the bank. Banks that have a high FDR may experience difficulty in meeting their financing obligations if a liquidity crisis occurs or a decline in credit demand occurs. This can cause an increase in NPF because customers may have difficulty paying back their financing.

(15) Disclosure of Islamic Social Reporting /ISR. FDR may influence ISR disclosure because banks that have high FDR may tend to focus on meeting their financial obligations rather than paying attention to their social and environmental responsibilities. However, good quality banks tend to pay attention to their social and environmental responsibilities without neglecting their financial obligations.

(16) Disclosure of Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR. FDR can influence CSR disclosure because banks that have high FDR may focus more on financial profits and pay less attention to social and environmental responsibilities. However, banks that have a lower FDR tend to pay more attention to their social and environmental responsibilities because they have more liquidity and freedom in making long-term investment decisions.

(17) Murabahah and Mudharabah Financing. FDR can affect Murabahah and Mudharabah financing because the higher the FDR, the more difficult it is for banks to provide financing to customers. This is caused by higher bank funding costs when FDR is high, so banks may reduce financing on certain products such as Murabahah and Mudharabah.

(18) Musyarakah Financing. FDR can affect Musyarakah financing because the higher the FDR, the more difficult it is for banks to provide financing to customers. This is caused by higher bank funding costs when FDR is high, so banks may reduce financing on certain products such as Musyarakah. However, if the FDR is low, the bank will have more funds to provide as Musyarakah financing.

(19) Financing of Small and Medium Enterprises/SMEs. FDR can affect SME financing because the higher the FDR, the more difficult it is for banks to provide financing to SMEs. This is caused by higher bank funding costs when FDR is high, so banks may reduce financing to SMEs. However, if FDR is low, banks will have more funds to provide as SME financing.

(20) Home Ownership Credit/KPR Financing. FDR can affect mortgage financing because the higher the FDR, the more difficult it is for banks to provide financing to customers who want to buy a house. This is caused by higher bank funding costs when FDR is high, so banks may reduce financing on mortgages. However, if the FDR is low, the bank will have more funds to provide as mortgage financing.

(21) Financing problems. FDR can influence the level of problematic financing in Islamic banks. If the FDR is high, the bank may experience difficulty in fulfilling the financing payment obligations that have been provided to customers, because it finances too many projects and does not have enough liquidity.

Therefore, banks must ensure that FDR remains within safe limits so that the risk of problematic financing can be minimized.

(22) Asset growth. FDR can also influence the growth of Islamic bank assets. If the FDR is low, the bank can have more funds to use in distributing more financing, thereby increasing the growth of bank assets. However, if the FDR is high, it will be difficult for banks to channel more financing, which can affect the growth of bank assets.

(23) Distribution of financing. FDR can influence the level of financing distribution in Islamic banks. If FDR is low, banks can channel more financing because they have more funds available. However, if FDR is high, banks may be more careful in channeling financing due to higher liquidity risk. Therefore, banks need to pay attention to FDR in order to balance financing distribution and liquidity risk.

(24) Placement of funds in SBIS. FDR can influence the placement of funds in SBIS by sharia banks. If the FDR is low, then the bank has more funds available to invest in other financial instruments, such as SBIS. However, if the FDR is high, the bank may choose to place funds in more profitable financing rather than SBIS.

(25) Return On Assets /ROA. FDR can also affect Return On Assets (ROA) in Islamic banks. If FDR is low, banks can channel more funds to invest in financial instruments that generate higher income, thereby increasing ROA. However, if the FDR is high, the bank may have to be more careful in channeling funds and choose investments that produce a lower ROA.

(26) Return On Equity /ROE. FDR can also affect Return On Equity (ROE) in Islamic banks. ROE measures the efficiency of using bank capital in generating profits. If FDR is low, banks can channel more capital to invest in financial instruments that generate higher income, thereby increasing ROE. However, if the FDR is high, the bank may have to be more careful in channeling funds and choose investments that produce a lower ROE.

(27) Return On Deposit /ROD. FDR can affect Return On Deposit (ROD) in Islamic banks. ROD is the rate of return or profit obtained by depositors from their savings in Islamic banks. If FDR is low, banks can channel more funds into financial instruments that generate higher income, thereby providing better ROD to depositors. However, if the FDR is high, banks may have to reduce the deposit interest rates given to depositors to manage credit and liquidity risks.

(28) Return of deposit. FDR can also affect Deposit Returns at Islamic banks. Deposit Return is income generated by banks from funds deposited by depositors. If FDR is low, banks can channel more funds into financial instruments that generate higher income, so they can provide better Deposit Returns. However, if FDR is high, banks may have to limit Deposit Returns to manage credit and liquidity risks.

(29) Financing risk. FDR can also influence Financing Risk in Islamic banks. Financing Risk refers to the possibility of loss or default on the part of the party borrowing money. If FDR is low, banks have more funds available to lend, which can increase Financing Risk. However, if the FDR is high, the bank may prefer to limit the amount of financing provided to reduce financing risk.

(30) Total financing. The effect of FDR on total financing is very significant, because the higher the FDR, the greater the possibility for banks to limit the distribution of financing due to lack of funds. Conversely, the lower the FDR, the greater the bank's possibility of increasing financing distribution because of the surplus funds it has.

(31) Total assets. The influence of FDR on total assets is also quite significant, because FDR is an important indicator used to measure bank capital adequacy. The higher the FDR, the lower the bank's capital adequacy, because most of the funds received are used for financing. Conversely, the lower the FDR,

the higher the bank's capital adequacy because most of the funds received can be used to increase bank assets.

Mapping Literature Review Studies around the Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) Determinant Variables in Sharia and Conventional Banking

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 18 influences of FDR on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO. The higher the BOPO, the greater the costs the bank incurs to operate its business. This can have an impact on FDR because banks may have to charge higher fees to their customers, so customers may look for alternative funding outside the bank. Conversely, the lower the BOPO, the more efficient the bank is in managing its costs, so that it can offer products with more competitive costs and attract more customers to save or borrow.

(2) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR. The higher the CAR, the safer the bank is in managing financial risks and minimizing the risk of bankruptcy. This can affect FDR because banks may be better able to offer more attractive products with lower interest, thereby attracting more customers to save or borrow. Conversely, the lower the CAR, the greater the risk of bankruptcy and the bank may have to charge higher fees to its customers.

(3) Third Party Funds/DPK. The higher the DPK, the more funds available for banks to offer products such as loans or investments. This can affect FDR because banks may be better able to offer products with lower interest rates, thereby attracting more customers to save or borrow. Conversely, the lower the DPK, the less funds available for the bank to offer products, so the bank may have to charge higher interest to its customers.

(4) Growth of Gross Domestic Product /GDP. The higher the GDP growth, the greater the potential for business growth and demand for bank loans. This can affect FDR because the higher the demand for loans, the more likely banks are to increase their loan portfolio, thereby increasing FDR.

(5) IPO. An IPO can influence FDR because it can open the door for a company to obtain new sources of funding, either through loans from banks or through selling shares to investors. If the company decides to obtain funding through loans, it will increase the bank's loan portfolio, thereby increasing FDR.

(6) Murabahah Margin. Murabahah margins can affect FDR because the higher the profit margin, the greater the profits the bank makes, thereby increasing the amount of funds available for banks to offer financing products, and can increase FDR.

(7) Mergers. A merger or merger between two or more banks can affect banking FDR. In general, mergers between banks that have a large depositor base can increase FDR due to an increase in the number of deposits accepted by the bank. However, if a merger is carried out between banks that have a small depositor base, this could reduce the FDR because the bank will face difficulties in obtaining funds from deposits.

(8) Own capital. Own capital or shareholder equity can influence banking FDR. The greater the bank's own capital, the lower the banking FDR because the bank can finance operational and investment activities with its own capital. However, if its own capital is low, the bank must rely on external funding, such as deposits, to finance operational and investment activities, so that FDR will increase.

(9) Net Operational Margini /NOM. NOM is the ratio between operating income and bank net productive assets. If a bank has a high NOM, this can increase bank profits and strengthen the bank's financial position, so that the bank can obtain funding at lower costs. On the other hand, if a bank has a low NOM, it

will be difficult for the bank to obtain funds from outside at low costs, so the bank tends to increase FDR.

(10) Net Interest Margin /NIM. If a bank has a high NIM, this shows that the bank is able to maximize income from the funding sources used, so that the bank can reduce dependence on external funding, such as deposits. On the other hand, if a bank has a low NIM, the bank will be more dependent on external funding to finance operational and investment activities, so that FDR will increase.

(11) Non Performing Financing /NPF. If a bank has a high NPF, this indicates that the bank faces high credit risk and must allocate most of its resources to deal with the problem. This can cause banks to have to rely on external funding, such as deposits, to finance operational and investment activities, so that FDR will increase.

(12) Transfer of Hajj funds to sharia banks. The Indonesian government has transferred the management of Hajj funds from BPKH to sharia banks. This can increase sharia bank funding due to an increase in the amount of funds managed. As a result, Islamic banks can obtain funding at lower costs and can reduce dependence on external funding, such as deposits. However, this can affect the FDR of conventional banks because conventional banks have to compete with sharia banks in obtaining funds from the public.

(13) Musyarakah Financing. Musyarakah financing is financing carried out with the principle of cooperation between the bank and customers in managing a business. In musyarakah financing, the bank provides funds to customers to invest in a project or business, and the resulting profits or losses are shared according to the initial agreement. Musyarakah financing can increase FDR at banks because banks must provide sufficient funds to finance projects or businesses run by customers.

(14) Murabahah Financing. Murabahah financing is financing carried out by purchasing goods and reselling them to customers at a price higher than the previously agreed purchase price. In murabahah financing, the bank provides funds to the customer to purchase the desired goods, and the customer pays the resale price in installments. Murabahah financing can increase FDR at banks because banks must provide sufficient funds to finance the purchase of goods desired by customers.

(15) Mudharabah Financing. Mudharabah financing is financing carried out with the principle of cooperation between the bank and the customer in managing a business, but the bank acts as an investor and the customer acts as the business manager. The profits generated are shared according to the initial agreement. Mudharabah financing can increase FDR at banks because banks must provide sufficient funds to finance projects or businesses run by customers.

(16) Return On Assets /ROA. The higher the ROA value, the greater the bank's profitability. An increase in ROA can increase investor confidence in bank performance, so that demand for banking products, including credit, can increase. This has the potential to increase FDR at banks.

(17) Return On Equity /ROE. The higher the ROE value, the greater the bank's profitability. An increase in ROE can increase investor confidence in bank performance, so that demand for banking products, including credit, can increase. This has the potential to increase FDR at banks.

(18) Transmission of a dual monetary system. If the deposit interest rate at a sharia bank is higher than at a conventional bank, then people tend to prefer to place funds in a sharia bank. This can increase deposits at Islamic banks and reduce FDR at conventional banks. However, if the loan interest rate at a conventional bank is lower than at a sharia bank, then people tend to prefer to borrow from a conventional bank. This can increase credit at conventional banks and increase FDR at these banks.

Conclusions and Suggestions

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: firstly, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2010 to 2023 which came from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 246 published journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the FDR ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 5 clusters and 174 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 55 topics, cluster 2 consists of 46 topics, cluster 3 consists of 31 topics, cluster 4 consists of 28 topics, and cluster 5 consists of 14 topics. Third, based on mapping studies literature review, there are 31 topics related to the influence of the FDR ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Mudharabah Deposits, Financial Sustainability Ratio/FSR, share prices, Islamic Performance Ratio/IPR, capital adequacy, zakat compliance, company profits, liquidity, Murabahah margin, profit management, profit sharing ratio on deposits, Non Performing Financing /NPF, Islamic Social Reporting /ISR disclosure, Corporate Social Responsibility /CSR disclosure, Murabahah financing, Mudharabah, Musyarakah, Small and Medium Enterprises/UKM financing, Home Ownership Credit/KPR financing, problem financing, asset growth, financing distribution, placement of funds in SBIS, Return On Assets /ROA, Return On Equity /ROE, Return On Deposit /ROD, deposit returns, financing risk, total financing, and total assets. And there are 18 topics related to the determinants of the FDR ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Operational Costs to Operating Income/BOPO, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, Third Party Funds/DPK, Growth of Gross Domestic Product /GDP, IPO, Murabahah margin, merger, own capital, Net Operational Marginal /NOM, Net Interest Margin /NIM, Non Performing Financing /NPF, transfer of Hajj funds to sharia banks, Musyarakah financing, Murabahah, Mudharabah, Return On Assets /ROA, Return On Equity /ROE, and the transmission of a dual monetary system.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer time span for research data so that The following research results can be obtained: first, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the results of the literature review study can be explained in a more complex way.

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